

DESIGNING CONSCIOUSNESS

WE FORMULATE OUR UNDERSTANDING OF CONSCIOUSNESS IN TERMS OF A PRECISE COMPUTABLE AND COMPREHENSIBLE FRAMEWORK IN ORDER TO EXPLORE AND STUDY PERCEPTUAL PROCESSING WITHIN ANY INTEGRATED SYSTEM MAINLY IN TERMS OF SIMPLIFIED ALGORITHMS, DIGITS AND STRINGS AND THREW OUT A MINIMALISTIC AND MITICULOUS METHODOLOGY . HERE, IT IS PROPOSED THAT CONSCIOUSNESS IS BUILT UPON COMPLEXITY WHICH ALLOWS INFORMATIONAL PROCESSING TO 'EVOLVE' AND DEVOLOPE MORE SUBTILE MECHANISMS . NEURAL NETWORKS BECOME A SIMPLE EMERGING COMPONENT WITHIN THE MECHANICS THAT CAN BE EXPRESSED AND COMPUTED IN TERMS OF EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS AND WOULD EXIST ONLY WHEN CONDITIONED BY THE PROCESSING OF INFORMATION . THIS WILL ALLOW US TO DESCRIBE EVERY POSSIBLE EXPERIENCE WITHIN ANY INTEGRATED SYSTEM IN TERMS OF SIMPLE ALGORITHMS THAT CAN THEN BE SYNTETHIZED (COMPUTED) INTO A LANGUAGE WHICH WE CALL THE 'DESIGN LANGUAGE' OR 'PERCEPTUAL LANGUAGE..

WE THEN ELABORATE AN INTERACTIVE 'MAP' IN ORDER TO ILLUSTRATE GRAPHICALLY OUR LANGUAGE AS A SEQUENTIAL COMPUTATION WHERE EACH 'STEP' WITHIN THE PROCESSING IS LABELED AS AN EVENT THAT CONSTITUTE AN ELEMENT IN THE OVERALL DESCRIPTION. WE FINALLY CONCLUDE OUR PROJECT BY VERY IMPORTANT IMPLICATIONS AND DISCUSS ABOUT VARIOUS APPLICATIONS.

The vague complexity behind Consciousness studied within Artificial intelligence and human bestows with frissons within the dulcet comely art of thinking^[1,23] to the extent of becoming a cutting-edge study field in which both Artificial intelligence and Neuroscience intently unite. Yet it inspired elegantly within the current progress of Theoretical Computer Science^[45,6] many to perceive and interpret the World differently^[7,89] out of its obvious harmony not only to establish the very own foundations of Computational Neuroscience^[90,11] but also to expand them beyond the reach of simple system modeling to pure creation and interpretation^[12,13,14] which helped bypass embarrassing problems such as the Hard problem of Consciousness^[15]. A constellation was constructed progressively around the development to include the seemingly odd postulate of 'computing reality' as our Centuries tended to follow this driving vector threw the important development that shed a blurry light on Consciousness and its structure purely threw representing it as informational processing which is now known today as the Time Slice theoretical framework^[16]. Following this thin developmental Lattice, we start to realize that despite the ambitious studies made so far, consciousness is still not holding a universal, computable definition that sheds light on the emergence and processing of sensory information Theoretically derived from a computational framework description nor how it is being structured and conditioned in order to 'emulate' (or namely 'integrate') and display sensory information and features to represent Reality which adds up to the very challenging task of understanding and simulating consciousness purely in terms of a computable entity and derive its various exploitations to potential subfields in AI Computational neuroscience^[17,18] and other related ideals that somehow commute when it comes for the need of a Universal unifying framework. We thus remedy that and propose a novel framework inspired from Theoretical computer science and AI paradigms that would enlighten us on the mysterious structure of consciousness by rendering it a computable entity. Hence, we strongly believe that in order to achieve such a transparent, perfectionated level of description unveiling the very own structure and nature of consciousness, each fragile and delicate 'step' has to be tracked, looked upon and maintained under controle for the study.

Within the poetry of these lines, we reduce Consciousness in terms of very simple unconscious informational processing within the shape of rules referred to as 'The Design Valley' that over time and under the influence of an evolving complexity devolops more subtle and sophisticated computable mechanics that would later be conditioned as a computable language made of algorithms and simple cellular rules namely threw the 'creative phase' which is a phase in which essential mechanisms such as neural networks emerge (thus emulated) to encode and express any given experience. Neural networks are thus said to emerge either in the form of evolutionary algorithms that add up to the computation or in terms of rules depending on the chosen processing configuration of the model. We finally generalize our computable Language to represent the processing in terms of a sequential computation model that would permit us to represent graphically an alternative 'map' that encodes the overall experience of the integrated subject and conclude by very important remarks in order to offer that new paradigm.

Design valley

Merely we began on the alluring poetical quest of Consciousness, stepping progressively deeper into the beating heart of our existence to address a deterministic description of radically collapsing theories^[19,20,21] within the very constructive backbone of its treasures. It thus remained a mystery, described vaguely by 'states'^[22,23], simple philosophical attributes and a lack of will and ambition to further dive deeper, generalize its mechanisms and unlock its profound ramifications. It remained shattered and blurred to say the least until computationalism started to approximate our thoughts by offering diversified perspectives and interactive simulations diving literally into a subtle reality^[24,25]. Yet the delivered sample was not enough to conclude the skepticism about the very own mysterious nature of Consciousness or even alter it while Theoretical Computer Science contains a rich, vast, unexploited sea of extremely interesting treasures to implement within the course of our computational neuroscientific studies about consciousness. As time fades away, fissures glow within the bright mirror of future with no possible, reconciling framework. Remarkably, behind the darkness that encompasses the different theoretical foundations of Computer Science leaks a profound mathematical realism and significance. It can be shown threw the Simulation Hypothesis^[26] for example (which in fact is a perfect description of that mathematical realism) that we can entirely recover our understanding of reality within translating it in simple Boolean algebraic concepts^[27] thus, to simplify the emotionally latent task of analysis to a machine to take charge of it but also to allow that specific machinery to evolve by itself and ultimately provide a transcendental amount of details that our simple limited vision can not yet grasp. Very ambitious empirical developments made in Digital physics has also already held the issue, motivated by the famous 'it from bit' philosophy^[28] yet none of them seemed to give much interest to the study of the most fundamental component of

nature, which is our Consciousness itself being very poorly understood. Thus, complexity predominated the transcendently large background in which the genesis of ideologies connecting complexity to consciousness has started trending. It came as a light-struck to envisage thus consciousness simply as an evolving processing structure in complexity that once upon an accumulated amount of information starts to become conscious within the vast realm of mathematics in which the overall perception, memory functioning, cognitive tasks, knowledge representation and pattern recognition are fundamentally encoded following the process of that evolving integrated system namely called the Design valley. It could then be argued that no better way to understand the deep mechanisms of such a phenomena would be to envisage the very own the expression of its complexity and mechanisms within a concise testable model that would later unveil an experimental methodology to study the overall structure of consciousness in terms of an 'evolving' computable language. Postulating then that we are among describing a complex processing and evolving system such as consciousness, we find out that Cellular processing^[29,30,31] for example are among the simplest methodologies for describing complex evolving processes including emergent behaviors which are synthetically essential for an overall review self-organized view on the system. Sensory information can initially and equally be considered as ordinary processed information evolving under a complexity measure within the theater of a lattice S being partitioned into equal sized finite sets P . We thus need to introduce a new kind of local function, $f: \mathbf{p} \rightarrow \mathbf{p}$ that maps the entire contents of a given set $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbf{P}$ at time t to another state of the same set of sites at time $t+1$. The function f clearly allows an informational exchange among all sites of a given set of the partition but would disallow communications between sites contained in different sets. In order to allow information to spread threwh the lattice, we first choose another partition P' , such that its set elements overlap those of the original partition P and another function f' that is of the same kind as f but acts on sets of P' and then keep alternating between applications of the global maps F and F' and then keeps alternating between applications of the global maps F and F' on successive iteration steps. Generally, we can envisage processing modeling within the borders of a one dimensional Cellular automaton, each site carries a value 0 or 1. The value $\mathbf{a}_i$ of the site at each position $\mathbf{i}$ is updated in discrete time steps according to an identical deterministic rule depending on a neighborhood of sites around it

$$\mathbf{a}_i^{(t+1)} = \phi [\mathbf{a}_{i-r}^{(t)}, \mathbf{a}_{i-r+1}^{(t)}, \dots, \mathbf{a}_{i+r}^{(t)}] \quad (1)$$

Each with $k=2$ and $r=1$. The simulation (namely the design valley) would then evolve from simple generated local rules to form global complex patterns including complex beaviors that can be modeld using A Complexity measure extracted in terms of entropy

$$d^{(x)} = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{x} \log_k N(X) \quad (2)$$

Where $N(x)$ gives the number of distinct sequences of X site values that appear for any given dynamical system computed within the Automaton.

$$\mathbf{u}_i^{t+1} = \text{sgn}\{\mathbf{Z}_2 + \mathbf{C}_2[|\mathbf{z}_1 + \mathbf{c}_1|(\mathbf{Z}_0 + \mathbf{b}_1\mathbf{u}_{i-1}^t + \mathbf{b}_2\mathbf{u}_i^t + \mathbf{b}_3\mathbf{u}_{i+1}^t)]\} \quad (3)$$

Where the eight added parametres $\{\mathbf{z}_0\mathbf{z}_1\mathbf{z}_2; \mathbf{b}_1\mathbf{b}_2\mathbf{b}_3; \mathbf{c}_1\mathbf{c}_2\}$ are given for each rule. As complexity grows, our valley can proceed to more complex creations and can thus design and emulate various paradigms explicitd in the form of algorithms and rules. Emergent self-organized behaviors generated by the evolution of complexity represent the most important part of the processing as it permits the creation and generation of new algorithms and rules from the previous processing. Self-organization can be more precisely studied and understood at this stage under the framework of a Structurally dynamical cellular automaton, (SDCA)^[32,33] which would unviel us an insight on how evolutionary and neural algorithms, essential for the experience of an integrated system emerge. This is an abstract model system in which the topological structure of the underlying lattice is dynamically coupled to the local site value configuration. The coupling is defined to treat geometry and value configurations on an approximately equal footing. The model allows for the study of true geometric self organization of information, and not merely geometric analogs which clearly owe their existence to a regularity of structure of the background lattice. This is by allowing the lattice itself to become a full participant in the dynamical evolution of the system. This is where conventionally it will be defined on a particular lattice network, the sites of which are populated with discrete-valued dynamic elements evolving under certain local transition function. Such a network with N sites is simply a general (undirected) Graph G of size N and is completely defined by the $(N \times N)$ connectivity matrix

$$l_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \text{ and } j \text{ are linked} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Using the graph metric function $\mathbf{D}_{ij} = \min_{\text{paths}}[\#\text{links}(i, j; \text{path})]$ we can write a general r -neighborhood Co value-transition rule 'f' for the information within our system in the form

$$\sigma_1^{t+1} = f[\{\sigma_j^t\} | j \in S_r^G(i)] \quad (5)$$

where $S_r^G(i) = \{j | D_{ij} \leq r\}$ is the radius- r graph sphere about the site- i . This gives the evolutionary property of the more general system

$$\begin{cases} \sigma^{t+1} = F_1[\{\sigma^t\}, \{l^t\}] \\ l^{t+1} = F_2[\{\sigma^t\}, \{l^t\}] \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

In which the changing value states and geometries are explicitly coupled. The complete system at time- t must now be specified by the state vector

$$|G \rangle_t = |\sigma_1^t, \dots, \sigma_N^t; \{l_{i,j}^t\} \rangle \quad (7)$$

The time-evolution of $|G \rangle$ then proceeds according to specifically determined transition rules as the most general rules which can be applied would definitely be invariant under all rotation and reflection symmetry transformations on local neighborhoods. We then can specify totalistic and outer totalistic value rules formally threw

$$\sigma_i^{t+1} = \phi_{\{a\}} \left(\sum_j l_{ij}^t \sigma_j^t, \sigma_i^t \right) \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\phi_{\{a\}}(x, A) = \begin{cases} \sum_a \delta(x + a, A) \rightarrow \text{totalistic} \\ a \sum_{a_1} \delta(x, A_1) + (1-a) \sum_{a_0} \delta(x, A_0) \rightarrow \text{outer totalistic} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

As the action on the state $|G \rangle$ is represented by

$$\hat{\Phi}_{\{a\}}^i |\sigma \rangle_t = |\sigma_1^t, \dots, \sigma_i^{t+1} = \phi_{\{a\}} \left(\sum_j l_{ij}^t \sigma_j^t, \sigma_i^t \right), \dots, \sigma_N^t \rangle \quad (10)$$

where local geometry altering rules can be recovered for any two sites selected i and j by restricting attention to site values of vertices contained within a 1-
sphere of either site; that is, to all $k \in S_1(i, j) = S_1(i) \cup S_1(j)$ where the link operators whose action on the state is represented by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Psi}_{\{\beta\}}^{ij} |l_{ij}^t \rangle &\geq |l_{11}^t, \dots, l_{ij}^{t+1} = \psi^{ij}, \dots, l_{NN}^t \rangle \\ \hat{\Omega}_{\{\varepsilon\}}^{ij} |l_{ij}^t \rangle &\geq |l_{11}^t, \dots, l_{ij}^{t+1} = \omega^{ij}, \dots, l_{NN}^t \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Global transition operators are then obtained by applying individual value and link operators to all sites and site pairs in the graph G :

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\Phi}_{\{a\}} |\sigma \rangle = \prod_i \hat{\Phi}_{\{a\}}^i |\sigma \rangle \\ \hat{\Psi}_{\{\beta\}} |l \rangle = \prod_{n < ij} \hat{\Psi}_{\{\beta\}}^{ij} |l \rangle \\ \hat{\Omega}_{\{\varepsilon\}} |l \rangle = \prod_{nn < ij} \hat{\Omega}_{\{\varepsilon\}}^{ij} |l \rangle \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Where the products for $\hat{\Psi}$ and $\hat{\Omega}$ need to be taken only over nearest and next nearest pairs respectively. Given the full value-topology transition rule Γ , defined by

$$|G \rangle_{t+1} = (\hat{\Omega} \hat{\Psi} \hat{\Phi}) |G \rangle_t = \Gamma |G \rangle_t \quad (13)$$

we can Consider patterns that emerge from simple value seeds starting from ordered 2-dimensional Euclidean lattices. A single non-zero site may represent a small local disturbance that then propagates outward, restructuring the lattice. With appropriately chosen Ts one can induce a rich spectrum of different time evolutions only slightly perturbed by very few concurrent link changes to ones in which the initial geometry becomes radically altered.

Figure 1: First five iterations of an SDCA emerging from simple seeds. Information is evolving until achieving a 'creative stage' mainly represented as a self-organized phase within the system which would enable the system to generate (namely 'emulate') various algorithms that contribute in the evolution of processing in a different manners expressed through rules or through deeper aspects of the system.

At this stage a high degree of geometrical organization, uniformity and connectivity of the lattice start appearing. The system exhibits a prolonged growth in complexity. Defining $\langle d \rangle \equiv$ average degree = average number of neighbors per site and an effective dimensionality $D_{Defec} \equiv$ ratio of the number of next-nearest to nearest neighbors, both of these measures increase in value in our model. Here, the evolution of systems starting from initial value states is generally difficult to follow visually, particularly for Ts that induce many structural changes and must therefore be studied indirectly. The simplest way is to chart the time-development by recording selected statistical measures. Thus, our Design Valley acquires a new creative structural perspective capable to organize, create, emulate and modify a given structure. Emulation here refers to the creative modeling of a given scenario through the arrangement and perceptual modeling of a given percept in order to represent a given experience (eg. Diving within the sea, feeling pain, thinking, etc...) through the emulation of several mechanisms within the processing to allow so and express the experience. The creative modeling and designing inventory then widely presented within a plateau would obviously expand to include more important properties such as Local Equivalence expressed where two local rules N and N^t become locally invariant under a transformation: $T: N \rightarrow N'$ iff the output u_i^1 of N after one iteration of any initial input pattern u_i^0 can be found by applying the transformed input $T(u_i^0)$ to rule N^t and then followed by applying the inverse transformation $T^{-1}: N' \rightarrow N$ to u_i^1 for any $t=1,2,\dots$. And also can be globally equivalent iff the output u_i^1 can be found for any t by applying the transformed input $T(u_i^0)$ to local rule N' followed by an inverse transformation $T^{-1}: N' \rightarrow N$ to $u_i^1 \forall t = 1, 2, \dots$ permitting various symmetry transformations. Modeling various repetitive behaviors for example is also quite essential for the understanding of principles like self-organization within our system as it can be achieved through the Cellular description of attractors. For a finite length l , the dynamic pattern evolving from initial state $x(0) = X^0 = (x_0^0, \dots, x_{l-1}^0, x_l^0)$ under any given rule N must eventually repeat itself within a minimum period. The set of repeated cellulars can be considered a periodic attractor which is characterized by an attractor period. Attractors are then extracted within a CA exhibiting global equivalent properties for example which potentially could contribute in the formation of fractals which is a well known property found in attractor dynamics. A more delicate observation of a given characteristic function $\%0_N^1$ Within the system reveals that nearly every graph of $\%0_N^1$ exhibit a fractal geometry where self-similar two dimensional substructures manifest themselves, going to infinity, as the number of cells $(l + 1) \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, they can explicitly also highlight the notion of time reversibility when taking an attractor $\Lambda(n)$ or an invariant orbit $\Lambda(n)$ of cellular automaton N with k consecutive bitstrings $\overline{x_1}, \overline{x_2}, \dots, \overline{x_k}$ belonging to $\Lambda(N)$ of automaton N to the last bit string $\overline{x_k}$ for a total k iterations. It follows the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{x_{k-1}} &= N^+(\overline{x_k}) \\ \overline{x_{k-2}} &= N^+(N^+(\overline{x_k})) \\ \overline{x_{k-3}} &= N^+(N^+(N^+(\overline{x_k}))) \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

*

$$\vec{x}_1 = N^\dagger \left(\underbrace{N^\dagger \left(N^\dagger \dots \left(\vec{x}_k \right) \right)}_{k-2 \text{ times}} \right) \dots \quad (14)$$

Where our Design valley has reached an important constructive realm of depth in details as among the self-organization inventory can be found different evolutionary

FIGURE 2. ENCODING GRAPHICALLY THE EVOLUTION OF VARIOUS PROCESSING MODELS PURELY IN TERMS OF ALGORITHMS . EACH COLOR REPRESENTS A SPECIFIC ALGORITHM CONDITIONED AND GENERATED BY THE PROCESSING USED BY THE CREATIVE PHASE TO EMULATE VARIOUS EXPERIENCES.

Paradigms which are said to be generated from the self-organization of the system and its creative phase that permits the construction of more subtle and complex mechanics. We can thus recover for example these evolutionary algorithms either in terms of rules or simply as a sequence within a sequential computable model followed by these processing as the SDCA processing has said to potentially demonstrate its capabilities in the modeling of these complex evolutionary tasks but also motivated by the proposed relations ^[34,35,36] in which we can inspire ourselves to recover the use of neural networks as modeled directly from the SDCA processing in order to express how basic emulation scenarios are generated within a conscious system threw the emulation of background mechanics that allow so . Following these lines , we first require to condition our processing model with a historic memory to be embedded in the CA dynamics by featuring every cell with a mapping of its states in the previous steps . Thus given transition rules (Φ) it is required that they are maintained unaltered unaltered and make them act on the cells featurd by a function of their previous states . Thus cells can be featurd by a weighted mean value of their previous states

$$m_i^{(T)}(\sigma_i^{(1)}, \sigma_i^{(2)}, \dots, \sigma_i^{(T)}) = \frac{\sigma_i^{(T)} + \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} a^{T-t} \sigma_i^{(t)}}{1 + \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} a^{T-t}} \equiv \frac{w_i^{(T)}}{\zeta(T)} \quad (15)$$

and the S values are obtained by rounding the m values : $s_i^{(T)} = \text{round}(m_i^{(T)})$, with $s_i^{(T)} = \sigma_i^{(T)}$ if $m_i^{(T)} = 0.5$. Memory becomes operative after $T = 3$, with the initial assignations $s_i^{(1)} = \sigma_i^{(1)}$, $s_i^{(2)} = \sigma_i^{(2)}$ for a general Cellular automata . For a reversible SCDA , Memory is embedded in links in a manner similar to that in state values , so the link between any two cells is featurd by a mapping of its previous values $l_{ij}^{(T)} =$

$\text{round}(m_{ij}^{(T)}, l_{ij}^{(T)} = \lambda_{ij}^{(T)}$ if $m_{ij}^{(T)} = 0.5$, after $m_{ij}^{(T)} = \frac{w_{ij}^{(T)}}{\zeta(T)}$ with

$$w_{ij}^{(T)} = \lambda_{ij}^{(T)} + \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} a^{T-t} \lambda_{ij}^{(t)} = w_{ij}^{(T-1)} + a \lambda_{ij}^{(T)} \quad (16)$$

Where the distance between any two cells in the historic model (d_{ij}) is defined in terms of l instead of λ values , so that l and j are direct neighbors if

$d_{ij} = 1$, and are next-nearest neighbors if $d_{ij} = 2$; $N_i^{(T)} = \left\{ \frac{j}{d_{ij}^{(T)}} = 1 \right\}$. With unchanged Transition rules operating on links.

an explicit modeling of modern neural paradigms ^[37,38,39] can thus be rendered possible for the system that can be expressed through rules . once we envisage the generation of a binary threshold automaton giving

$$x_i(t+1) = \theta \left(\sum_j w_{ij} x_j(t) - \tau_i \right) \quad (17)$$

Where $x_i(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ is the value of the i^{th} neuron at time 't'. $\{w_{ij}\}$ would be the set of the synaptic weights , each of which can be either positive or negative depending on whether a given synapse is excitatory or inhibitory ($w_{ij} = 0$ if no synapse exists between neurons 'i' and 'j'). τ_i is the threshold value for the i^{th} neurone , and $\theta(x)$ is the unit step function :

$$\theta(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Endowed with a learning rule

$$w_{ij}(t+1) = \begin{cases} w_{ij} & \text{if } R - \text{unit response is correct} \\ w_{i(t)+\eta x_i} & \text{if } R - \text{unit response is 0 and should be 1} \\ w_{i(t)+\eta x_i} & \text{if } R - \text{unit response is 1 and should be 0} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Where $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$ is our learning constant that controls the learning rate. this can be thought of as a fully connected , symmetrically-weighted field ($w_{ij} = w_{ji}$) where the value of the i^{th} neurone is updated according to

$$S_i(t+1) = \text{sgn} \left(\sum_j w_{ij} S_j(t) - \tau_i \right) \quad (20)$$

Where we have used bipolar variables $S_i \in \{+1, -1\}$ instead of binary variables to simply some of the subsequent equations giving

$$\text{sgn}(x) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ -1 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Giving the symmetry synaptic weight matrix where we can simply represent the whole in a sample energy landscape (also known as the Hopfield network ^[40,41]) where it can be expressed as the energy function

$$\mathcal{E}[\{S_i(t)\}] = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{ij} w_{ij} S_i(t) S_j(t) + \sum_i S_i(t) \tau_i \quad (22)$$

In the double sum over indices 'i' and 'j', we assume that $w_{ii} = 0 \forall i$ where we could also take $w_{ii} = 1$ but this would simply add a constant term to $\mathcal{E}$ where we show that the Lyapunov function , we assume that the net evolves asynchronously and calculate the explicit change in $\mathcal{E}$ that is induced by a change in the i^{th} neuron

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \mathcal{E}_i &= \mathcal{E}[\{S_i(t+1)\}] - \mathcal{E}[\{S_i(t)\}] = -\left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_j (w_{ij} + w_{ji}) S_j(t) - \tau_i \right] (S_i(t+1) - S_i(t)) \\ &= -\eta_i S_i(t+1) \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_j (w_{ij} + w_{ji}) S_j(t) - \tau_i \right] \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Where

$$n_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } S_i(t+1) = +S_i(t) \\ 2 & \text{if } S_i(t+1) = -S_i(t) \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Then if we assume weight set is symmetric then

$$\Delta \varepsilon_i = -\eta_i S_i(t+1) \left[\sum_j w_{ij} S_j(t) - \tau_i \right] \quad (25)$$

Since from equation (22) gives

$$\left(\sum_j w_{ij} S_j(t) - \tau_i \right) S_i(t+1) \geq 0 \quad (26)$$

As we conclude that

$$\Delta \varepsilon_i \leq 0 \quad (27)$$

Where ε is a non increasing function of time.

Memory storage capacities for the Neural network can also be recovered throu a pseudo-code implementation for any given set of patterns $\{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$ where the i^{th} pattern is encoded by the neural values $\{S_i^{(P_1)}, S_i^{(P_2)}, \dots, S_i^{(P_n)}\}$ defines the synaptic-weight matrix

$$w_{ij} = w_{ji} = \begin{cases} \sum_{k=0}^n S_i^{(P_k)} S_j^{(P_k)} & i \neq j \\ 0 & i = j, 0 \leq i, j \leq n. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Wher the running pseudo-code initializes the net with the pattern P^*

$$S_i(t=0) = S_i^{P^*}, \quad 0 \leq i \leq N-1 \quad (29)$$

As the update rule iterrates until the net converges

$$S_i(t+1) \text{sgn} \left(\sum_{j=0}^N w_{ij} S_j(t) \right) \quad (30)$$

This leads us to current designing paradigms that expand our perspective such as Multilayer perceptron given by

$$R - S^1 - S^2 - S^3 \quad (31)$$

Where the number of inputs is followed by the number of neurons in each layer.

Figure 3: Illustrating the creative potential exhibited by self-organization and SDCA processing in the generation and modeling of an artificial neural network inspired from evolutionary algorithms to serve as background mechanics encoding important emulation and simulation models .

We can then envisage deriving a backpropagation algorithm for a multilayer model giving

$$\mu_j^p = \sum_k w_{jk} \sigma_k^p \quad (32)$$

And yields an output

$$h_j^p = f_a(\mu_j^p) = f_a\left(\sum_k w_{jk} \sigma_k^p\right) \quad (33)$$

Where $f_a(x)$ is the sigmodal threshold function but with a parameter a added to control the steepness of the curve

$$f_a(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-ax}} \quad (34)$$

Where that the derivative $f'_a(x)$ also taking a rather simple form

$$f'_a(x) = a f_a(x) (1 - f_a(x)) \quad (35)$$

As the i^{th} output neuron recives input

$$\mu_i^{\mu} = \sum_j w'_{ij} h_j^p = \sum_j w'_{ij} f_a\left(\sum_k w_{jk} \sigma_k^p\right) \quad (36)$$

and produces an output

$$\mathbf{o}_i^p = f_a \left(\sum_j \mathbf{w}'_{ij} \mathbf{h}_j^p \right) = f_a \left(\sum_j \mathbf{w}'_{ij} f_a \left(\sum_k \mathbf{w}_{jk} \sigma_k^p \right) \right) \quad (37)$$

With the chain rule guiding the input-to-hidden connections

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{\mathbf{w}_{jk}} &= -\eta \frac{\partial D}{\partial \mathbf{w}_{jk}} = -\eta \sum_p \frac{\partial D}{\partial \mathbf{h}_j^p} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_j^p}{\partial \mathbf{w}_{jk}} \\ &= \eta \sum_p \left(\sum_i^i -\mathbf{o}_i^p \right) f'_a(\mu_i^p) \mathbf{w}'_{ij} f'_a(\mu_j^p) \sigma_k^p \\ &= \eta \sum_{p,i} \Delta_i^p \mathbf{w}'_{ij} f'_a(\mu_j^p) \sigma_k^p \\ &= \eta \sum_p \Delta_j^p \sigma_k^p \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Where

$$\Delta_j^p = f'_a(\mu_j^p) \sum_i \mathbf{w}'_{ij} \Delta_i^p \quad (39)$$

The framework can be largely adapted and sequentially expanded to tackle combinatorial optimization problems essential for the creative processing. Thus, Given an input graph, represented as a sequence of n cities in a two dimensional space conceding a standard TSP $\mathbf{s} = \{\mathbf{X}_i\}_{i=1}^n$ where each $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we are concerned with finding a permutation of the points $\boldsymbol{\pi}$, termed a tour, that visits each city once and has the minimum total length. We define the length of a tour defined by a permutation $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ as

$$L(\boldsymbol{\pi}|\mathbf{s}) = \|\mathbf{x}_{\boldsymbol{\pi}(n)} - \mathbf{x}_{\boldsymbol{\pi}(1)}\|_2 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \|\mathbf{x}_{\boldsymbol{\pi}(i)} - \mathbf{x}_{\boldsymbol{\pi}(i+1)}\|_2 \quad (40)$$

Where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes ℓ_2 norm. We use the chain rule to factorize the probability of a tour as

$$p(\boldsymbol{\pi}|\mathbf{s}) = \prod_{i=1}^n p(\boldsymbol{\pi}(i)|\boldsymbol{\pi}(< i), \mathbf{s}) \quad (41)$$

Using reinforcement learning provides an appropriate paradigm for training neural networks for combinatorial optimizations through policy based RL to optimize our pointer network's parameters denoted $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Our training objective is the expected tour length given an input graph $\mathbf{s}$. formally $J(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{E}_{\boldsymbol{\pi} \sim p_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\cdot|\mathbf{s})} L(\boldsymbol{\pi}|\mathbf{s})$. The policy gradient of the objective is formulated using Reinforce algorithm^[42]

$$\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} J(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{E}_{\boldsymbol{\pi} \sim p_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\cdot|\mathbf{s})} [(L(\boldsymbol{\pi}|\mathbf{s}) - b(\mathbf{s})) \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \log p_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\boldsymbol{\pi}|\mathbf{s})] \quad (42)$$

The choice of an auxiliary network can be thought following

$$L(\boldsymbol{\theta}_v) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B \|\mathbf{b}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}_v}(s_i) - L(\boldsymbol{\pi}_i|s_i)\|_2^2 \quad (43)$$

Emulation scenarios and details that can be modeled using neural mechanisms and their efficiency can also be extended to surface reconstruction from scattered data, range data, or shape from shading^[43,44] to recover, reconstruct, and match shape^[45,46] to represent and model objects^[47,48] to estimate motion of objects and classify them^[49,50] and for object segmentation^[51,52] through the simple use of our artificial neural nets. using the proposed model^[53] to visualize

object construction and representation within our system through namely a transformation module and a representation module quintessentially illustrating several aspects of Consciousness and its mechanics. Starting from a pointcloud that embeds the shape of the object to be modeled, a volumetric representation is obtained using the multilayer feedforward network. The surface of an object is described by a set of zeros in the output response of the network, while the interior or exterior of an object is mapped to a negative or positive value, respectively. Namely, this primitively relates somehow to geometrical modeling concepts [ref] thus inputs here are 3-D coordinates (x, y, z) of a point and their combinations and returns the 3-D coordinates of the corresponding transformed point. The purpose is to build a volumetric description of a 3-D object. One network is used for each represented object. The network receives as inputs the 3-D coordinates x, y and z of a point and their combinations (x^2, y^2, z^2, xy, yz and xz) and outputs a value proportional to the distance between the point given as input and the modeled object surface. The surface of an object is, thus, described by a set of zeros in the output response of a network mainly through a MLFNN or through using a self-organizing representation module.

FIGURE 4 ILLUSTRATION OF HOW NEURAL NETWORKS EMULATE PROGRESSIVELY A RANDOM SHAPE WHICH THEMSELVES ARE BEING CONDITIONED TO BE EMULATED AS FUNDAMENTAL BACKGROUND MECHANICS FOR THE RUNNING OF THE ALGORITHMIC PROCESS AND ARE THUS SIMPLY BEING COMPUTED.

For several animation models mainly physically realistic dynamical animation models, the numerical simulation of the associated equations of motion leads to a computation of a discrete-time dynamical system of the form

$$\mathbf{s}_{t+\delta t} = \Phi[\mathbf{s}_t, \mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{f}_t] \quad (44)$$

Where these equations express the vector $\mathbf{s}_{t+\delta t}$ of state variables of the system at time $t+\delta t$ in the future as a function Φ of the state vector $\mathbf{s}_t$, the vector $\mathbf{u}_t$ of control inputs and the vector $\mathbf{f}_t$ of external forces acting on the system at time t . Thus a Physics-based animation through the numerical simulation of a dynamical system requires the evaluation of the map Φ at every timestep, which usually involves a non-trivial computation. Our task is to construct neural networks that approximate Φ in the dynamical system (previous eq st). We thus use a backpropagation to train feedforward networks $\mathbf{N}_\Phi$ to predict future states using super timesteps $\Delta t = n\delta t$ while containing the approximation error so as not to appreciably degrade the physical result of the resulting animation. analogue to the equation (44), the basic emulation step is expressed in

$$\mathbf{s}_{t+\Delta t} = \Phi[\mathbf{s}_t, \mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{f}_t] \quad (45)$$

where the trained emulator network $\mathbf{N}_\Phi$ takes as input the state of the model, its control inputs, and the external forces acting on it at time t and produces as output the state of the model at time $t+\Delta t$ by evaluating the network. After each evaluation, the network control and force inputs receive new values and the network state inputs receive the emulator outputs from the previous emulation. Training the neuroanimator is thus rendered possible when considering input vector x and output vector y . In the general case, the input vector $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{s}_0^T, \mathbf{f}_0^T, \mathbf{u}_0^T]^T$ comprises the state of the model, the external forces and the control inputs at time $t=0$. the output vector $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{s}_{\Delta t}$ is the state of the model at time $t = \Delta t$, where Δt is the duration of the super timestep. To generate each training example, we would start the numerical simulator of the physical based model with the initial conditions $\mathbf{s}_0^T, \mathbf{f}_0^T, \mathbf{u}_0^T$ and run the dynamic simulation of n numerical time steps δt such that $\Delta t = n\delta t$. This enables in principle to generate an arbitrary large set of training

examples by repeating this process with different initial conditions. Writing a sequence of emulation steps following (Eq.43) is thus rendered possible and is expressed following

$$\mathbf{s}_{i+1} = N_{\phi}[\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{f}_i]; \quad 1 \leq i \leq M \quad (46)$$

Where i indexes the emulation step, and $\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{f}_i$ denote respectively the state, control inputs and external forces in the i th step. A discrete objective function can thus be defined following

$$J(\mathbf{u}) = \mu_u J_u(\mathbf{u}) + \mu_s J_s(\mathbf{s}) \quad (47)$$

a weighted sum of a term J_u that evaluates the controller $\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2, \dots, \mathbf{u}_M]$ and a term J_s that evaluates the motion $\mathbf{s} = [\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{M+1}]$ produced by the Neuroanimator using $\mathbf{u}$ as already demonstrated.^[54]

Such a framework permits us to experimente a more immersive analysis using the very own Foundations of Artificial Neural networks to observe the emulation of various interesting emulation scenarios from the emulation of our Neural networks as Background mechanics. This enables us to visualize how the system at such a growing complexity phase can devolope deeper mechanisms and emulate more fundamental paradigms^[55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62] within our programming within the course of the developement in which we can express the mechanisms and the generated experience of these mechanisms in terms of evolutionary algorithms.

Now, since our neural factory is fundamentally based, and modeled within our Cellular automaton and where our Neural paradigms can either be formulated in terms of evolutionary algorithms, rules or simply threw a Cellular neural network, we can thus generalize the overall developpement to the more apprehandable framework of Language Theory which permits to study the system in various interesting cases and perspectives threw

$$\phi: \Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma \quad (48)$$

As to represent the global form of the local (one-dimensional) mapping $\phi: \Sigma^{2r+1} \rightarrow \Sigma$, where $\Gamma = \Sigma^N$, the ensemble of configurations generated after t ' iterations (which we will refer to as the finite-time limit set of the rule ϕ) $\Omega_t = \Omega_t[\phi]$ is given by

$$\Omega_t[\phi] = \phi^t \Gamma \quad (49)$$

Where the finite-time set of an arbitrary CA rule $\phi, \Omega_t = \Omega_t[\phi] = \phi^t \Gamma$ is a regular language for all t '. To this end, we then would consider an explicit construction for a given elementary rule defined by :

$$\begin{cases} 000 \rightarrow 0, & 001 \rightarrow 1, & 010 \rightarrow 0, & 011 \rightarrow 0, \\ 100 \rightarrow 1, & 101 \rightarrow 1, & 110 \rightarrow 0, & 111 \rightarrow 0. \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

Thus it can be typically represented using simple digits and letters for an alphabet A , which is a nonempty set of symbols. For an n -tuple of symbols of A defined on the string A . If $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ so we write the string $\mathbf{s}(A) = a_1 a_2, \dots, a_n$; where the length of the string is the number of symbols of which it is composed and is written $|\mathbf{s}(A)| = n$. we then are able to define the abstract finite automata M specified by three sets A, Σ, Σ^* and a state-transition function $\phi: \Sigma * A \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ such that

$$\begin{cases} A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\} \text{ is a finite input alphabet} \\ \Sigma = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n\} \text{ is a finite set of states} \\ \Sigma \subset \Sigma^* \text{ is the set of output (or accepting) states} \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

Given an automaton M that starts at σ_1 and any finite string $\mathbf{s} \in A^*$, $\phi^*(\sigma, \mathbf{s})$ will represent the final output state and a dynamical rule corresponding to $\Sigma * \Sigma^* \dots * \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma$ and where ' n ' specifies the number of cells needed to define the neighborhood of a given cell as given $N\{\bar{i}\}$ to be the neighborhood about cell $\bar{i}$, the transition rule is not generally rewritten then as

$$\sigma_{\bar{i}}(t+1) = \phi(\sigma_j \in N\{\bar{i}\}) \quad (52)$$

Which determines the transition between states where individual cells evolve iteratively according to a fixed, and usually deterministic function of the current state of that cell.

reduced and simplified into digits and string, the current developpement evolopes our understanding of neural networks and informational processing within a simplified computable language that we call 'perceptual language'. each algorithm can thus be considered as an 'event' within the evolutionary computational model.

The perceptual valley

Our constant classical dependence upon Neural networks and the ordinary picture of the brain lies within its transcendental processing properties and since we now know that we can reformulate the entire architecture in terms of simple evolutionary algorithms (thus neural mechanics generated by consciousness and conditioned by processing and the experience that they encode) within the construction of an evolutionary language, another picture can thus be envisaged in order to elaborate quietly a map, thus, a graphical representation of our sequential computation that we will define as the 'Perceptual valley'. serving us to represent every process occurring within the system in perfect depth and details. We thus let S be the set of events of our sequential computation $e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_n, \dots$, and relations and X be the set of manipulated state variables essential components for the experience. We start by assuming that X is static — no new variable is created as the computation proceeds — And that all these variables are initialized before event e_1 . For deriving a causet, we represent the computation as the sequence $((R_1, W_1), (R_2, W_2), \dots, (R_n, W_n), \dots)$, Where R_i and W_i are the sets of variables respectively read and written by event e_i . We call this 'RW-sequence': a causet derived from it is an 'RW-causet'. Following the meditation idea above, an RW-causet is readily built: there will be a directed edge from e_i to e_j if and only if $W_i \cap R_j \neq \emptyset$: e_j reads at least one of the state variables written by e_i , say variable x . We express these facts by the notion $e_i \xrightarrow{x} e_j$. In conclusion, the set of edges of the raw RW-causet would be given by:

$$E = \{(e_i, e_j) \in S^2 \mid \exists x \in X. e_i \xrightarrow{x} e_j\} \quad (53)$$

We then should consider also an RW-causets in which an event that reads variable x is influenced only by its most recent writer event. In this case, the set of edges contributed by variables x becomes as it has been already pointed^[63]

$$E_x = \{(e_i, e_j) \in S^2 \mid e_i \xrightarrow{x} e_j \wedge \neg \exists k (i < k < j \wedge e_k \xrightarrow{x} e_j)\} \quad (54)$$

Giving us an elegant transition from fat causets to 'thin' graphs. Hence, Deriving these causets from deterministic sequential computational models becomes possible

FIGURE 5 IN ORANGE : REPRESENTATION OF THE ORDERED SEQUENTIAL COMPUTATION ACTIVITY AND FLOW WHICH RENDERS PROGRESSIVELY VISIBLE THE TOY MODEL (THE BLUE REGION) AS THE SEQUENTIAL 'FLOW' IS CONSTRUCTED PROGRESSIVELY IN TERMS OF AN RW-CAUSED COMPUTATION.

Discussions

We delved within the realm of Theoretical Computer Science and Artificial intelligence to elaborate a computable language and Universal description for Consciousness. It is thus observed that Consciousness is mainly based upon informational processing that define its emergence, structural and creative properties and mechanics that allow consciousness to be modeled, envisaged and studied in various ways for any conditioned, integrated system within the borders of a computable language made of rules and algorithms once it achieves a 'creative phase' in which it could emulate and simulate mechanics that themselves would encode essentially the experience and can all be thus expressed in terms of evolutionary algorithms within the processing of a sequential language. The computation of Neural networks, backpropagation and evolutionary algorithms all thus depend upon the chosen and programed processing model and are thus considered to be emerging when chosen the right processing condition that will shape and compute these mechanics in the form of either rules or evolutionary algorithms. These evolutionary algorithms are said to develop progressively under the given augmenting complexity of the system along the processing to define the complex mechanics that are exhibited by Consciousness and we can thus attribute a computable picture for consciousness which solenely provides a first true unifying model to study integrated systems where neural networks are said to emerge from self-organized processing to define the particular mechanics of consciousness and where we can dispense the need of Computational Neuroscience and the classical processing picture of the brain knowing that we have the fine processing elements that constitute its architecture. It is then proposed to delve further within the computation of our language in terms of representation as it is used to elaborate a 'map' of consciousness by labeling each delicate process (or step or rule) in terms of an event within a sequential computation to replace the latent, complex and 'primitif' standard image of the brain. Consciousness is thus not residing within the brain but within a specific processing conditioning that can be mapped (namely called the 'Design valey'.) We thus believe that we are intimately close of a major advance which is not going to be simply restricted within the elegant borders of Artificial Intelligence and Computational Neuroscience but that also provides a framework to compute nearly every possible experience within any integrated system, mainly, to study, evaluate and process 'reality' in terms of simple algorithms, attributing them an event within the generalization of our language in terms of a sequential computation and running the overall

picture as a computable map rather than having to be dependant upon the classical framework provided by Neuroscience which can be generalized in terms of simple algorithms within a computable framework and where visual models of 'reality' or even the simple but made complex concept of 'spacetime' can be recovered throu these digital mechanics . This Novel framework would defently allow consciousness to be explicitied in simple digits and strings , and thus be explored , altered , manipulated and redescivered once generalized in terms of a sequential computer code as it concentrates and coordinates the creative potential of Integrated analysis directly to the core and the heart of its manufacturing and processing throu explicitly structuring it rather than having to adapt to the classical brain picture to offer a new genesis.

Appendix

The choice of evolutionary algorithms is a representative choice based upon the fundamental configuration of the cellular processing and thus is said to emerge particularly from that subjective processing model . Several real-life concepts can thus be rendered computable and can be considered as participant parameters within the evolution of the computable language . 'Life' and evolution abstractly can thus be encoded when looking upon basic biological systems are subject to point mutations localized changes in DNA as well as to high levels of mutations such as copying an entire gene and then introducing changes in it . We can define it as an arbitrary algorithm that transforms or maps the original organism into the mutated organism taking an input as and organism and producing an output as a mutated organism for any n -bit mutation program with probability 2^{-n} in order to have the total probability of mutation be ≤ 1 .

This leads us to define a second crucial concept which is the mutation distance which is the distance measured in bits and defined to be $\log_2$ of the probability that a random mutation will change A to B from the organism A to B . Using the famous AIT method , we see that nearly $H(B|A)$, the size in bits of the smallest self-delimiting program that takes A as input and produces B as output gives

$$H(B|A) = -\log_2 P(B|A) + O(1) = -\log_2 \left[\sum_{U(p|A)=B} 2^{-|p|} \right] + O(1) \quad (A.1)$$

Where $|p|$ denotes the size in bits of the program p and $U(p|A)$ denotes the output produced by running p given input A on the computer u until p halts as the rate of the mutation evolution could be evaluated throu the busy beaver function

$$BB(N) = \max_{H(k) \leq N} k \quad (A.2)$$

Where the program-size complexity or algorithmic information content $H(k)$ of k is the size in bits of the smallest self-delimiting program p without input for calculating k

$$H(k) = \min_{U(p)=k} |p| \quad (A.3)$$

Where here again $|p|$ denotes the size in bits of p and $U(p)$ denotes the output produced by running the program p on the computer u until p halts.^[64]

if we could choose our mutations intelligently ,evolution would be much rapid . For the halting probability Ω [ref]. This implies to define a different Busy Beaver function BB' based on Ω for a fixed recursive/ computable enumeration $\{ p_i: i = 0, 1, 2, \dots \}$ without repetitions of all the programs without input that halt when run on U . Thus

$$0 < \Omega = \Omega_U = \sum_i 2^{-|p_i|} < 1 \quad (A.4)$$

and we get the following sequence $\Omega_0 = 0 < \Omega_1 < \Omega_2 \dots$ of lower bounds on Ω

$$\Omega_N = \sum_i 2^{-|p_{iN}|} < 1 \quad (A.5)$$

where in the following two equations $|p|$ denotes the size in bits of p , as befor .

the computation can be generalized in terms of a programing language , thus capable of expressing any algorithm , we can combine subroutines for algorithmic information we have

size of program to calculate x and y
 $\leq$ size of program to calculate x
 $+ \text{size of program to calculate } y.$

With a self-delimiting programs we have

$$H(x, y) \leq H(x) + H(y) + C \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $H(\dots)$ denotes the size in bits of the smallest program for U to calculate ...

Appendix B (Graphic design)

Another crucial concept is the Design capabilities^[65,66] which are essential to encode geometrical data and which also can be generalized algorithmically in order to study, model, and understand generally aspects encoded within our neural mechanics to represent visual data threw using more complex and detailed algorithms threw considering a convex combination of points $S = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ enabling us to capture the geometrical modeling and emulation mechanism of geometrical patterns of the form

$$\lambda_1 p_1 + \dots + \lambda_n p_n$$

Where $\lambda_i \geq 0$ and $\sum \lambda_i = 1$ where the convex hull of S would be the set of all convex combinations of our events labeled in an ordered manner to constitute an ordered computation. the overall structure can then subtly be recovered threw the use of the Incremental algorithm technique or the Graham Gift wrapping algorithm^[67] which become formal attributes of the computation. Geometrical data can be simulated within the system when We oriente our intrest particullary in The angles sequence

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{3n})$$

Of T which is said to be the list of all $3n$ angles of T sorted from smallest a_1 to largest a_{3n} in order to show how the different brain regions contribute in forming the percept after it's computation. We can then compare two different triangulations of S to get a more general picture of the geometry. for two triangulations T_1 and T_2 . we say that T_1 is 'fatter' than T_2 if the angle sequence of T_1 is lexicographically greater than T_2 . In other words, if $(a_1, \dots, a_{3n})$ is the angle sequence for T_1 and $(b_1, \dots, b_{3n})$ for T_2 . then there is some $1 \leq k \leq 3n$ where $a_i = b_i$ for all $i < k$ and $a_k > b_k$. Thus

$$(20^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 65^\circ, 70^\circ, 130^\circ)$$

Is fatter than

$$(20^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ, 130^\circ)$$

Because $65^\circ > 60^\circ$ which enables us to determine perfectly a complete picture of consciousness as a terrain where we computed threw the previous Graham Scan the percept via the convex hull and examined threw the Delaunay triangulations in details the different parts contributing in it's creation which portioned the interior of the convex hull. a dual picture can be studied using Voronoi diagram $Vor(p)$ of a site p in S is :

$$Vor(p) = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid |x - p| \leq |x - q| \text{ for all sites } q \text{ in } S\} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Where $\|p - q\|$ denotes the (Euclidian) distance between points p and q in the plane. In words, $Vor(p)$ would be the set of all points x that are at least as close as p to another site q in S . Geometrical data can then be finally detailed and computationally defined as the metric space $\mathbf{X}$ with distance function d with $\mathbf{k}$ being a set of all indices and $(P_k)_{k \in K}$ as a tuple (ordered collection) of non empty subsets (the sites) in the space $\mathbf{X}$. The Voronoi cell, or region R_k associated with the site P_k is the set of all points in $\mathbf{X}$ whose distance to P_k is not greater than their distance to the other sites

P_j , where j is any index different from k . In other words, if $d(x, A) = \inf\{d(x, a) | a \in A\}$ denoting the distance between the point x and the subset A then

$$R_k = \{x \in X | d(x, P_k) \leq d(x, P_j) \text{ for all } j \neq k\} \quad (B.2)$$

In order for the system construct the algorithm, given a constructed Delaunay triangulation $Del(S_k)$ with k sites, we find the set of triangles whose circumcircles contain the new site p . The union of these triangles is a triangulated polygon as we then delicately remove the diagonals of this polygon and add edges from p to each of the vertices of the polygon to obtain the new Delaunay triangulation, now containing p .

Figure 6 Illustration for different computational geometrical data acquired and computed by the system through the use of algorithm. Input represents events which are still not computed until the system develops a Delaunay triangulation or Voronoi algorithm to compute the convex set.

The strong connection between the convex hull and Delaunay can be explicated when computing in one higher dimension where given a point set S in the xy -plane, the Delaunay triangulation (S) would be exactly the projection to the xy -plane of the lower convex hull of points

$$(x, y, x^2 + y^2) \quad (B.3)$$

Where we can recover the Delaunay triangulation of a point set in the plane from the projection of the lower convex hull of these points on the paraboloid. Given the geometry of the paraboloid, from multivariable calculus, the equation of the tangent plane at a point (a, b) is given by

$$z = 2ax + 2by - a^2 - b^2 \quad (B.4)$$

As if the plane is shifted upward (in the Z direction) by a distance of r^2 , one obtains a new plane π given by

$$z = 2ax + 2by - a^2 - b^2 + r^2 \quad (B.5)$$

From conic geometry, this plane π intersects the paraboloid along an ellipse. The projection of this ellipse onto the xy -plane obtained yields to

$$(x - a)^2 + (y - b)^2 = r^2 \quad (B.6)$$

This leads us to determine also the relation between the Delaunay triangulations and Voronoi diagram found within the Delaunay complex of a finite set S will be isomorphic to the nerve of Voronoi diagram

$$Del = \{ \sigma \subseteq S \mid \bigcap_{u \in \sigma} V_u \neq \emptyset \} \quad (B.7)$$

We then say the set S is in general position if no $d+2$ of the points lie on a common $(d-1)$ -sphere. The assumption implies that no $d+2$ Voronoi cells have a non-empty common intersection. Equivalently, the dimension of any simplex in the Delaunay complex is at most d giving delaunay triangulations superimposed on the Voronoi diagram.

We then can recover also the computational construction of simplexes (which are fundamental for computing topological data from percept properties) for illustrating geometrical reasoning by Considering $\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_k$ as points in our space of computation. A point $\mathbf{x} = \sum_{i=0}^k \lambda_i \mathbf{u}_i$ will be the affine combination of the $\mathbf{u}_i$ if the λ_i sum to 1. It is a k -plane if the $k+1$ points are affinely independent by which mean that any two affine combinations, $\mathbf{y} = \sum \lambda_i \mathbf{u}_i$ and $\mathbf{x} = \sum \mu_i \mathbf{u}_i$ are the same iff $\lambda_i = \mu_i$ for all i . the $k+1$ points are affinely independent iff the k vector $\mathbf{u}_i - \mathbf{u}_0$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$ are lineary independent. AN affine combination $\mathbf{x} = \sum \lambda_i \mathbf{u}_i$ is a convex combination if all λ_i are non-negative. A k -simplex would be the convex hull of $k+1$ affinely independent points $\sigma = conv\{\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_k\}$ where we have $\tau \leq \sigma$ if τ is a face and $\tau < \sigma$ if it is a proper face of σ .

Figure 7: Illustrating a simplex computation within the system

A simplicial complex is then a finite collection of simplexes K such that $\sigma \in K$ and $\tau \leq \sigma$ implies $\tau \in K$, and $\sigma, \sigma_0 \in K$ implying $\sigma \cap \sigma_0$ is either empty or face of both with the underlying space $|K|$ being the union of simplexes together with the topology inherited from the ambient Euclidian space in which the simplexes generally live. We can then define a simplicial map (which is the equivalent of continous maps between topological spaces)

$f: |K| \rightarrow |L|$ defined by

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n b_i(x) \varphi(u_i) \quad (B.8)$$

Where φ is our function for the vertex map such that $\varphi: \text{Vert } k \rightarrow L$ that induced the simplicial map and b_i as our barycentric coordinates x in k . we can then feel free to subdivide our simplex throu a barycentric subdivision $L = \text{Sd}K$ as other simulation methods such as alpha complexes can be recovered.

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